

Title: Strong AI vs. Machine Learning for Adding Cognition to Applications – Example in ECommerce

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INTRODUCTION:

Machine Learning technologies are becoming increasingly popular as the backbone of building AI applications. However, Machine Learning is just a subset AI -well suited to classification and pattern recognition tasks. Strong AI technologies, based on symbolic reasoning, are also necessary additional components to combine with Machine Learning to build cognitive, more intelligent, applications. An application in ECommerce is used to demonstrate the limitations of Machine Learning and the benefits of leveraging a broader range of symbolic AI technologies to engage users, increase conversion rates and revenue.

AIM:

To highlight the limitations of Machine Learning technologies, and to demonstrate the benefits of using a broad spectrum of AI methods and tools to build more intelligent applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees and k-nearest neighbors algorithm are compared with Knowledge-based/Semantic techniques to increase the performance of Search, Recommendations, and User Experience in ECommerce.

RESULTS:

100 A/B tests were conducted. 50% increase in conversion and 25% increase in average order value were achieved by combining Strong AI techniques with Machine Learning to improve the user experience across 3 different ECommerce web sites.

CONCLUSIONS:

According to our initial test results, combining Machine Learning and Strong AI techniques can significantly increase the performance of Search, Recommendations and User Experience in ECommerce.

KEYWORDS:

Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees and k-nearest neighbors algorithm, Ontologies, Inferencing, Knowledge Representation, ECommerce, User Experience.

BIOGRAPHY:

Faramarz Farhoodi is the CEO of Sapient Shopping, Inc. He has held senior management and C-level roles in global companies such as Amazon, IAC, Pert Systems, Logica, and Auction.com.

He has a B.Sc. Honors in Econ and an M.Sc. in CS/AI from the UK. He served on the Science and Engineering Research Council and the IEE's C4 AI Committee in the U.K for 3 consecutive years. Faramarz has led more than 700-person years of ground-breaking work in AI since 1984 – being the lead architect of an AI-based military command and control system developed for a consortium of European (NATO) countries. He has published numerous papers in reputed journals and has chaired several conferences and workshops in AI.